

Constructing Marginal Abatement Cost Curves for Scottish Peatlands:

Data integration approach and challenges

Daniel Urban, Klaus Glenk, Daniel Fletcher

SRUC

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Summary

- This report provides a detailed overview of methods, data sources, data management approaches and limitations of the up-to-date work on cost effectiveness of peatland restoration projects funded in Scotland under the Peatland Action (PA) grant programme. The dataset and corresponding data management protocol constitute deliverables and inputs into further analysis of the *CentrePeat* project under the Scottish Government’s (SG) Strategic Research Programme (SRP), the European Union’s *Wet Horizons* project and the “*Understanding Peatland Restoration Costs and Contractor Capacity*” report commissioned by *ClimateXChange*. At its centre stands the individual site-level database developed under the “*Costs of Peatland Restoration*” line of work by Glenk et al., (2020,2021,2022).
- For the purpose of exploring and evaluating relevant spatial factors of variation in peatland restoration costs and activities, an extensive list of spatially explicit of environmental, meteorological, topographic and infrastructural datasets was identified and sourced. Using various GIS tools, the information from these data sources was extracted and merged with the SRUC/PA cost database.
- A detailed overview of the data used is presented in the “Data Sources” section. The methods and assumptions used are in the “Merging the cost database with external data” part followed by “Main limitations” outlining challenges with the chosen approach accompanied by practical examples.
- The extended database functions as a basis for construction of the *marginal abatement cost curves* (MACC), a multivariate explanatory regression model and a spatial cost prediction model for determining cost effective pathways for scaling up future peatland restoration efforts.

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Rationale

The unit costs (i.e., costs per hectare) of restoring degraded peatlands have been found to vary considerably across sites and projects (Glenk et al., (2020,2021,2022)). At least parts of the variance in unit costs may be due to site-specific environmental factors that determine restoration complexity, and site-specific factors that determine access costs to sites. Therefore, a better understanding of unit cost variation can be instrumental in identifying cost effective pathways to scale up future restoration efforts.

This report provides details on the work on identifying the spatial and environmental factors affecting the costs of peatland restoration, and subsequent gathering and linking of data from a range of public sources that is relevant for uncovering and interpreting the underlying patterns.

Cost effectiveness of peatland restoration puts the public and private expenditure on these efforts into context of delivery of their intended benefits: either from the perspective of restored area or mitigated GHG emissions. These concepts are put into practical use by constructing *Marginal Abatement Cost Curves* (MACC) for Scottish peatlands (Eory et al.,2018; Glenk & Martin-Ortega, 2018). This methodology allows one to rank available restoration options by descending cost effectiveness, and thus help with prioritisation in allocation of limited resources. However, unlike in other applications of this approach, the individual restoration measures applied on each degraded peatland site need to work in accord, to deliver the desired benefits. Their combinations are specifically selected to address the specific conditions that each site is facing. Thus, this novel approach to MACC analysis focuses on identification of condition-specific clusters, which in turn depends on the availability and use of spatial data discussed in this document.

The information presented in this report also draws on correspondence, meetings and data exchange with a range of partners and colleagues from other relevant institutions. The cost database has been constructed using data and guidance from NatureScot/Peatland Action¹. The queries regarding the spatial data aspects of the restoration projects and issues described below have been consulted with the PA spatial data team in the format of regular meetings. The updates and applications of the additional environmental data are a result of exchange with partners from the James Hutton Institute (JHI) and the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology (CEH).

Factors included in analysis and spatial data sources

The analysis builds on the previous work on understanding variation in site-specific restoration costs. For this study, the publicly available spatial data identified as potential predictors of variation in peatland restoration costs come from several sources listed in [Appendix Table A1](#).

It is necessary to know location and dimensions (shape) of restored sites to be able to assign spatially explicit data to them. However, due to difficulty to reliably match many of the cost database sites with their [Peatland Action polygon](#) counterparts ([Main Limitations](#)), the site shape needed to be assumed. As all the sites selected for this analysis reported a UK National Grid location, representing a centroid for each site, and a restored site area (in hectares) was reported, we assumed that all sites were a circle of “restored area” centred at the grid location. This circle was then overlaid with the relevant spatial data and the data extracted. For example, to add the average number of ‘snow days’ expected on a site, we overlay the site circles on the

¹ We would like to acknowledge Peatland ACTION/the [Peatland ACTION Data & Evidence](#) team at NatureScot for their active support of this work.

[HADUK](#) grid of climate observations and extract the average snow days associated with the site. The section '[Merging cost database with external data](#)' contains full details of the methodology.

Data Sources

Cost Database

The core source of information used and described in this report is the individual site-level database developed under the “*Costs of Peatland Restoration*” line of work by Glenk et al., (2020,2021,2022). Each observation in the database corresponds to a discrete restored site funded with in the NatureScot Peatland Action (PA) grant scheme, identifiable by a site reference number and its grant reference number (Grant ID). The restoration projects may consist of one or several restored sites as well as one or several phases and sets of restoration measures (individual activities). On top of the standard grant award procedure, additional “top ups” of funds are allocated to projects when required. The individual restored sites within these broader projects are identifiable by a site reference. Due to the fact, that in the period before 2021 there was no unified methodology for naming the sites, a key had to be developed for creating a unique site reference (UID) while constructing the database. The database, in its most recent form, consists of detailed information on project costs and measures, originating from 408 application forms, 289 final reports and 171 monitoring protocols. As the true restoration costs are only revealed in the final reports, those are the database observations that were considered for analysis. Due to data reliability issues described later in this document, only 236 of these observations are complete and reliable enough to be used for further analysis.

Peatland Action Open Data Spatial Database

The online data mapping resource of NatureScot PA contains up to date spatial files with both the [centroids and polygon shapefiles](#) of restored peatland sites. A centroid represents a site centre point, that should correspond to the site grid reference in the cost database. It should also correspond to the centres of the shapefile polygons. The polygon files contain not only the location, but also spatial dimensions (shape) of each site with a restoration outline. The areas (in hectares) of these shapes should then correspond to the total restored areas of each site in the cost database, and thus act as a basis for the cost per hectare calculations. The [non-spatial spreadsheets](#) available on the PA website also contain information on total project areas, costs & completion timeframes.

Additional Spatial Data

The digital maps, containing information added to the cost database using GIS cropping and extraction tools were identified and downloaded from various public sources. This data was classified into four categories: Meteorology, Landscape Features, Peat Condition and Site Characteristics. The complete list of the variables used, their units, classes and links to sources, is available in the Appendix [Table A1](#). The approaches to extracting useful information from data of varying formats are presented below in [Merging the Cost Database with External Data](#). Specific issues that emerged during this process are discussed in [Data management Challenges: Practical Examples](#).

Data Management

For approximately half of the sites restored before the funding round of 2020/2021 the information on the location (site centroid) and total area restored, reported in the final project reporting forms, does not match the location and area of the site polygons held by NatureScot

PA. Thus, two parallel approaches to matching spatial/environmental data to the restoration cost records were taken:

1. Use the site location and area from the project reporting and assume the site outline to be circular. Then extract the spatial information by overlaying and cropping the maps over the new circular polygons.
2. Manually match the cost database observations that don't perfectly match with the PA polygons.

The former approach is rather crude but allows us to work with (almost) the entire cost database. The latter approach leaves us with much fewer reliable matches, but the true restoration outlines give us much more precise information on site-specific conditions that drive variation in restoration costs. Running the cost estimation model on the subset of the observations with precisely identified matches will in the following step of the analysis work as both a robustness check, and a base for a hybrid approach – where we could work with a combination of actual PA polygons if existing, and circular outlines in cases where true outlines are unavailable.

Merging the cost database with external data

The process of merging the NatureScot PA cost database with other spatial data involved the following steps:

1. The site grid references in the cost database were converted to Easting-Northing coordinates (using standard UK coordinate reference system EPSG:27700) and converted to a GIS point shapefile (using QGIS software package version 3.16).
2. The circular polygon shapefiles with the centre point being the actual site centroids with a total area corresponding to the reported restored area (in NatureScot PA final reporting forms) were created within the GIS framework.
3. The maps containing spatial environmental information were overlaid over the circular polygon layer and cropped into the shape of the sites (Figure1).
4. For the microclimatic variables (snow days, temperature, wind speed), topography (elevation, slope, ruggedness) and remoteness, an average value per site was calculated (for raster maps that means the total value of each variable for all raster cells in each site divided by the number of cells). For land cover categories, firstly the raster picture was converted into a vector polygon shapefile by smoothing the cell edges with a fineness down to 15 meters. A total area of each category per site was calculated and recorded as a separate variable (for all the land cover types that a specific site did not contain the variable values were zero). The areas of each category were divided by the total site area to arrive to a ratio of the site that has the particular land cover. The total length of outlines of individual land cover features was calculated to account for terrain heterogeneity (assuming that the more patchy the site is the longer the outline of the individual features). Similarly for the peatland condition map, a total area of each site that is peatland was calculated, individual peatland condition categories were recorded and ratios per site calculated. The bare peat ratio and floodplain/surface water area ratio were calculated as a ratio of the peatland per site rather than the total area of the site. Similarly, average peat depth was considered only for peatland area of each site. Finally, sites were assigned to a biogeographical region based on the centroids' precise location.

- The data was downloaded from the GIS software into a spreadsheet and merged back into the cost database using a unique site identifier (concatenated from a unique site ID and a report type). The further steps of analysis/ model and figure construction were completed in Excel, STATA and Python packages, respectively.

Figure 1: An example of populating the circular polygons with the cropped spatial features (In this case different colours represent individual land cover classes).

Data modifications

For peatland conditions, land cover classes and biogeographical zones the variables taken from the original data sources were pooled into more general categories to increase the model's ease of interpretation. For example, all landcover classes associated with forest were classified as one 'forest' category in the model, see [Appendix tables A2-A4](#) for more details.

For the costs to be comparable across all the sites, the total cost figure per site was divided by the total site area to arrive at a cost per hectare estimate. The costs have been deflated to 2020 levels using consumer price index (CPI) values from the [Office of National Statistics](#).

Main limitations

A major source of uncertainty is related to large variation in detail and rigour of reporting of the restoration process via application and reporting forms. Several reports are missing crucial details that make them invalid for further analysis, thus limiting the power of related studies.

Each project that has been granted funding by NatureScot can be identified via a grant reference number. Thus, the sites that have been restored within the same restoration grant share a same reference number. However, throughout the duration of projects, the definitions of sites often change. This includes both the number of sites within a grant, and the area of identified sites can both increase or decrease based on what is currently considered feasible/priority. Therefore, the

information entailed in project application forms can only be compared to final forms if these changes were sufficiently documented.

For deriving site area and overlay with GIS information, the circular site outline approach was chosen due to difficulty to reliably link a substantial number of the sites from the cost database with spatial data from Peatland Action that contains both centroids and site outlines. The grant reference numbers are often inconsistent between cost database and spatial information, and the number, area, account of applied measures and grant amounts often do not match between the information sources. Consequently, we had to manually “triangulate” matches between sites in the cost database and sites in the spatial data from Peatland Action, which was both time consuming and without guarantee of being free of error.

Due to a lack of a unified methodology for calculation of a total area of a restoration site, over time and across sites in the database, the account of area restored provided in the reporting form can be only treated as approximate. Sites for which the reported areas were missing, unclear or otherwise impossible to work with were removed from the analysis. As mentioned above, the site areas were in some cases also pooled together within the same project, and thus arriving at a reliable area estimate for the individual sites was difficult.

The format in which the type, unit and (unit or total) cost of restoration measures is reported also varies as application and reporting forms were updated over the years, and depending on reporting efforts invested by grantees. For example, the installation of wave dams has been reported either as the total number of individual dams, the total length of all the dams combined, or the total area covered by the specific type of dams. Wave dams also feature only in later editions of application and reporting forms. Such issues with reporting complicate measure-specific analysis of restoration cost. For example, differences in units in which measures are reported make judgment on measure intensity in a restoration site challenging if not impossible.

Data management challenges: Practical Examples

This section discusses several specific issues outlined above in detail and uses specific examples to illustrate the complexity of considerations during the data amalgamation process.

Site-Specific Observations

The individual restored sites within the broader projects (identified by a GRANT ID) are identifiable by a site reference (Site name). Since in the period before 2021 there was no unified methodology for naming the sites, (for example, project 501102 site 1, site 2...vs. project 501102 eastern site, western site), (Table 1) a key had to be developed for creating a unique site reference (UID) while constructing the database.

Table 1 Example of a site naming discrepancy (illustrative)

Grant ID	Site name	Site UID
501102	1	1
501102	2	2
501102	3	3
501103	Eastern Site	1
501103	Western Site	2

Figure 3 Examples of features that do not have any links to other spatial data sources.

Alignment of Spatial files: Mismatch between the site outlines and restoration polygons

The process of drawing the site outlines, creation of site polygon shapefiles, calculation of site centroid points and reporting areas and locations in the project final reporting forms in many cases happened independently of each other, and thus misalignment in total areas and dimensions of these features emerged. For example (Figure 4), in the PA list of projects, the project 501614 is reported to have restored 128,3ha of peat, while the total area of the site polygons (orange patches) amounts to 149.05 ha. The final report forms for 6 sites of this project do not report the areas of sites individually but show a total restored area as 197.9 ha.

Figure 4: An example of a project with a misalignment between the restored site outlines (red line) and site polygon area shapefiles (orange areas)

The example below (Figure 5) shows a section of the restoration efforts in the Forsinard Natural Flows National Part in Caithness and Sutherland. These overlapping features are apparently a result of a several phases of interconnected works on a singular line of restoration endeavours, but the four sources of spatial data provide contradicting information. From the twelve site centroids (pink dots) that come from the cost database, six belong to project 501172 with the total area of 180.3 ha, four sites to project 500972 with 85.69 ha and two to project 501266 that amount to 98.03 ha. At the same time, two of the sites from project 501172 share a site reference but report two different restored areas (30.96 or 22.4), while the latter site is also counted under project 500972. This is evidence of double counting of restored areas in certain cases where projects overlap.

The orange site polygons (PA site outline polygons) show 3 individual sites belong to project 501633 with a total area of 416 hectares. An older PA file containing site polygons (crimson red shapes) shows 4 sites belonging to project 501895 with a total area of 93.7 hectares. Three of these four sites overlap with some area the of the orange polygons mentioned above. One stands separately. The site outlines (red line) roughly correspond to these four sites, but with a buffer margin. This cluster of projects illustrates the issues that affect how rigorous the following steps of the analysis can be. The site-specific costs per restored hectare can only be accurately calculated if restored areas are precisely reported. Secondly, if the site locations, number and dimensions are not clear, then extrapolating and adding further explanatory spatial data becomes challenging and substantial error in the reported estimates can be expected.

Figure 2 An example of conflicting accounts from various data sources.

Current and Future Work

The expanded cost database is continuously updated both in terms of length and width and is used as backbone of several lines of interlinked work. As of 2024, the following processes are ongoing:

Expansion of the cost database

The cost database is continuously being updated with new observations as new project reports become available from Peatland Action. The data needs to be manually translated from the project reporting forms into a spreadsheet. As the forms report for all the work done within the scope of the grant allocation, individual site-level costs, measures and locations need to be identified and catalogued into the database in a consistent manner.

Data cleanup, identification of issues and merging

Due to the reasons outlined in the above sections, much of the observations in the database lack a clear link between site-specific measures, costs and site locations/dimensions. Identification and solving of these issues requires time, effort and communication. As the database grows in length and dimensions, so does the requirement for manual checking and confirming of the new inputs as of the attached protocol.

Identification and amalgamation of further data sources

As the discussion on the factors relevant for peatland restoration itself is ongoing, so is the process of searching for spatial data sources that might satisfy the conceptual requirements. Further, mapping of peatland extent, conditions, quality, depth, land cover, land use and emission inventories is an iterative process and any amendments to existing datasets will be incorporated into the current database to keep it up to date.

MACC conceptual work and case study utilising Scottish data

The site condition-specific MACC approach is dependent on both the local context (scale, use, type and reason for peat degradation), but also the data availability and quality. The current conceptual framework has been developed with Scotland in mind and the primary use of the cost database in the following stage of the work is to operationalize the data to construct and interpret the curves.

Spatial cost prediction model

Identifying the factors that are relevant drivers of spatial variation in costs of peatland restoration opens an opportunity for construction of a model that uses this data as parameter inputs for projections of cost levels for potential future restoration of (yet degraded) peatlands. A grid-based spatial protocol is being developed in order to classify peatland conditions into discrete clusters (as an output of the MACC work), that will, in turn, be used to create cost-efficient pathways for scaling up restoration efforts.

Conclusion

This report serves as an intermediate update on the progress in the ongoing work on data collection and management within the broader stream of research aimed at understanding the peatland restoration costs, measures and factors affecting the current and future restoration efforts conducted by the team at SRUC & colleagues. Communicating the details of the approaches and challenges faced during the current phase of the research is instrumental in aligning the work with the objectives and efforts of all the public and private actors engaged in the peatland restoration process, resolving the outstanding issues, sharing resources and streamlining future restoration projects.

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Appendix

Table A2: Complete list of variables, classes and data sources merged with the cost database during the described data amalgamation process.

Category	Class	Variable	Source
Meteorological		Average wind speed per year (m/s)	Had-UK-Grid
		Average annual rainfall (mm)	Had-UK-Grid
		Average daily temperature per year (C)	Had-UK-Grid
		Minimum daily temperature per year (C)	Had-UK-Grid
		Average days of snow cover per year (nb)	Had-UK-Grid
Peat Quality		Ratio of site that is bare peat (%)	NatureScot
		Average peat depth (cm)	James Hutton Institute
		Total carbon content in soils per site (kg)	James Hutton Institute
	Peat Condition areas	Forest (ha)	NAEI
		Cropland (ha)	NAEI
		Extraction (ha)	NAEI
		Eroded (ha)	NAEI
		Grassland (ha)	NAEI
		Modified Bog (ha)	NAEI
		Near Natural Bog (ha)	NAEI
	Settlement (ha)	NAEI	
Landscape		Land cover heterogeneity (m)	NatureScot
		Ratio of site that is floodplain/surface water (%)	Scottish Environment Protection Agency
		Terrain ruggedness (index)	Ordnance Survey
		Average slope (%)	Ordnance Survey
		Average elevation (m)	Ordnance Survey
		Remoteness/wilderness (index)	NatureScot
		Minimum distance to any road (m)	Ordnance Survey
	Land Cover	Woodland (ha)	NatureScot
		Shrubs (ha)	NatureScot
		Grassland (ha)	NatureScot
		Bogs (ha)	NatureScot
		Mires & Fens (ha)	NatureScot
		Other (ha)	NatureScot
Site characteristics	Biogeographical Zones (dummies)	Argyll	NatureScot
		Central Belt	NatureScot
		Isles	NatureScot
		Central Highlands	NatureScot
		East Coast	NatureScot
		Northern Highlands	NatureScot
		Southwest	NatureScot
		Flow Country	NatureScot

Table A3 Inventory peatland condition classes pooled into larger categories

Variable	Inventory categories
Forest	Forest
Cropland	Cropland
Eroded	Eroded
Modified	Modified bog
Near Natural	Near natural bog
Other	Other Peatland, Settlement
Grassland	Intensive Grassland, Extensive Grassland
Extraction	Industrial Extraction, Domestic Extraction

Table A4 Land cover classes pooled into larger categories

Variable	Land Cover Categories
Woodland	Woodland fringes and clearings and tall forb stands, Broadleaved deciduous woodland, Highly artificial coniferous plantations, Mixed deciduous and coniferous woodland, Lines of trees, small anthropogenic woodlands, early stage woodland and coppice, Coniferous Woodland
Shrub	Arctic, alpine and subalpine scrub, Temperate and mediterranean-montane scrub, Temperate shrub heathland, Riverine and fen scrubs
Blanket Bogs	Raised and blanket bogs
Other	Inland cliffs, rock pavements and outcrops, Arable land and market garden, Built-up, Bare field, Windthrow, Littoral sediment (predominantly saltmarsh), Coastal dunes and sandy shores, Coastal shingle, Rock cliffs, ledges and shores, Surface standing and running waters
Mires & Fens	Valley mires, poor fens and transition mires, Base-rich fens and calcareous spring mires
Grassland	Dry grasslands, Mesic grassland, Seasonally wet and wet grasslands, Alpine and subalpine grasslands

Table A5 Biogeographical zones pooled into larger Restoration zones

Restoration Zones	Biogeographical Zones
Argyll	Argyll West and Islands
Central Belt	West Central Belt
Isles	Coll, Tiree and the Western Isles, Orkney and North Caithness, Shetland, Western Seaboard
Central Highlands	Central Highlands, Cairngorms Massif, East Lochaber, Loch Lomond, The Trossachs and Breadalbane
East Coast	North East Coastal Plain, North East Glens, Eastern Lowlands
Northern Highlands	North West Seaboard, Northern Highlands, Western Highlands
Flow Country	The Peatlands of Caithness and Sutherland
Borders	Western Southern Uplands and Inner Solway, Border Hills